

A NEW INTERFERING AGENT IN SANCHIS' TEST FOR FLUORINE

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The isolation and identification of a material present in a typical vegetable carbon which interferes in Sanchis' method of estimating fluorine is described.

In the course of our studies on the removal of fluorides from drinking water with paddy husk carbon, it was observed that the colour of zirconium-alizarin lake was not bleached by sodium fluoride, dissolved in tap-water, percolated through a column of paddy husk carbon. This was interpreted to mean that during the course of percolation through the carbon, the sample of water had acquired an interfering agent from the paddy husk carbon, which did not permit the reaction between the dissolved fluoride and the zirconium-alizarin lake to take place. A number of ions has been known to interfere with the reaction of dissolved fluorine with the zirconium-alizarin lake (Sanchis, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1934, 6, 134; Willard and Winter, *ibid*, 1933, 5, 7). The permissible concentration of some of these interfering ions is given in Table I.

TABLE I

Ions.	Permissible conc.	Ions.	Permissible conc.
Cl ⁻	500 p.p.m.	Ca ⁺⁺	500 p.p.m.
SiO ₂	50	Fe ⁺⁺⁺	5
SO ₄ ⁼⁼	500	Mg ⁺⁺	500
S ⁼	2	Al ⁺⁺⁺	5
HCO ₃ [']	500	Mn ⁺⁺	200
PO ₄ ⁼⁼	5		

In addition to the above ions, large amounts of organic matter have been known to interfere by causing precipitation of the zirconium-alizarin reagent. The sample of tap-water, which was first passed through a cation-exchange resin on the hydrogen cycle and then percolated through a column of paddy husk carbon, was analysed for the various interfering ions, and it was found that none of the ions, known to interfere with the reaction between the dissolved fluoride and the zirconium-alizarin lake, was present in a concentration higher than the permissible limit. Consequently, the unbleaching of the zirconium-alizarin lake was assumed to be due to some other interfering agent, not reported hitherto. The present communication deals with the identification of the new interfering agent.

Some Properties of the Interfering Agent.—The interfering agent is completely soluble in water, and is not volatile with steam, as it cannot be removed by filtration or by boiling.

The substance is organic in nature, as it can be destroyed by ashing the residue left after evaporating the tap-water percolated through a column of paddy husk carbon.

The interfering agent is an anion, as determined by the use of ion-exchange resins (Kenneth and William, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1947, 9, 19; Samuelson, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1939, 116, 328) and as indicated by the data given in Table II.

TABLE II

Fluorine added (p.p.m.).	Fluorine found (p.p.m.)		
	TW passed through C.	TW passed through C, passed through H ⁺ exch. (neutralised).	TW passed through C, passed through H ⁺ exch. and then passed through anion ex.
0.6	0.0	0.0	0.4
1.0	0.0	0.2	1.0
1.4	0.3	0.3	1.4
1.8	0.45	0.45	1.7
2.2	0.5	0.5	2.0
2.4	0.6	0.6	2.2

The small amount of interference remaining may be tentatively attributed to the incomplete removal of the anion by the exchanger, probably due to the incomplete ionisation of the anion.

The interfering agent being anion is further confirmed by the observation that it forms an insoluble salt with calcium which is soluble in dilute sulphuric acid, and is oxidisable with both acid and alkaline permanganate.

After oxidation with acid or alkaline permanganate, the substance no more behaves like an interfering agent, as shown by the data given in Table III.

To counteract the possible effect of permanganate, fluorine standards with the same amount of permanganate in tap-water were also put up side by side.

TABLE III

	Set I		Set II	
	Fluorine (p.p.m.)		Fluorine (p.p.m.)	
	added.	found.	added.	found.
Tap-water passed through carbon	0.6	0.8	0.6	0.9
+ CaCl ₂	1.4	1.1	1.4	1.6
	2.0	1.7	2.0	1.9
Tap-water passed through carbon	0.6	0.55	0.6	0.9
+ KMnO ₄ .	1.0	0.85	1.0	1.2
	2.0	1.90	2.0	1.9

Isolation of the Interfering Agent.—Since the calcium precipitate was very small in quantity (1.5 g.) even when about 8 litres of the treated water were boiled with calcium chloride, only traces of the material were present and still capable of interfering.

Attempts were made in four different directions to examine the nature of the material and to develop tests by which its presence could be easily tested :

(1) The aqueous extract of the carbon was evaporated to dryness in the presence of a little alkali, and tests were conducted on this residue.

(2) A very dilute ($N/400$) solution of sulphuric acid, instead of the effluent from the hydrogen-ion exchanger, was percolated through the bed of carbon as the acid would be expected to extract out the interfering material more effectively.

(3) The aqueous extract was boiled with a solution of calcium chloride and tests were conducted on the precipitate formed.

(4) The aqueous extract was percolated through a cation exchanger and then through a bed of an anion exchanger. The latter bed which was found to retain most of the interfering material was eluted with a solution of alkali and tests were conducted on the residue obtained by evaporating the solution.

Identification of the Interfering Agent.—The residue in all these cases gave identical tests. It was treated with ether and the ether extract evaporated to dryness, taken up in hot water, filtered and tested for fluorine. No inhibition of bleaching was noticed. The residue from the ether extract gave reactions which pointed to the possible presence of tartaric or related hydroxy-acid. Thus, it charred with concentrated sulphuric acid; an aqueous solution gave a yellowish brown colour with ferric chloride and reduced alkaline permanganate through the green manganous stage. The absence of mirror test or ferrous test ruled out the possibility of the interfering agent being tartaric acid. The substance formed potassium and calcium salts which were insoluble in water. With resorcinol and concentrated sulphuric acid, it gave a red ring, a test for many hydroxy-acids. This test has been found the most sensitive for the interfering material and holds good even in very dilute solutions, so that it can be applied straight-away to the water treated by the carbon to see whether the interfering material is present. (When the interference is removed, as, for example, by passing the water through ion-exchange resins, no red ring is formed with these reagents.) The acid extract of the residue gave, like all α -hydroxy-acids, coloration with β -naphthol in concentrated sulphuric acid, a blue colour first formed turning to orange on dilution.

Since tartaric acid is known to be absent, another hydroxy-acid, which forms an insoluble potassium salt and may be present, is saccharic acid. Tests were made to find out if this material was the interfering agent. In fact, tests for saccharic acid like cobalt nitrate colour reaction, iodoform test and β -naphthol test were responded to by this material.

Preparation of Derivatives.—Out the elute from the anion exchanger, the phenylhydrazine derivative was prepared and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $20S^{\circ}$ (lit. m.p. 210°). From the same elute, a dye was prepared with phenylhydrazine-*p*-sulphonic acid. It dyed silk pinkish yellow just like saccharic acid.

Interference of known Hydroxy-acids.—These tests appear to show that the interfering material is an organic hydroxy-acid and that it can be detected in solution by resorcinol or β -naphthol in sulphuric acid. It was thought desirable at this stage to see whether pure simple organic acids inhibited the bleaching of zirconium lake by fluorine.

As a preliminary measure, to a solution containing different amounts of fluorine ranging from 0.6 to 2.0 p.p.m. were added 5 c.c. of 0.2% tartaric, citric, oxalic, malic and saccharic acids. These, as well as similar solutions not containing these acids, were treated with the usual Sanchis' solutions. Of these, citric, oxalic and malic acids inter-

ferred in the opposite direction, giving higher values for fluorine, and hence eliminated. Tartaric acid inhibited the bleaching to some extent, while saccharic acid interfered much more, a small trace being sufficient to give a low value for fluorine. Though tartaric acid had to be eliminated in this particular case as the mirror test was not obtained, different concentrations of tartaric and saccharic acids were tried and the interference in each case determined. Finally, 100 c.c. of each of these solutions were evaporated to dryness, ignited and made up to the original volume and put up for fluorine estimation by Sanchis' method. As is shown in Table IV, in all the instances, interference was completely removed. Similarly, the solutions treated with calcium chloride and filtered off from the precipitate formed also lost the interference.

TABLE IV

Fluorine found (p. p. m.)						
Fluorine added (p. p. m.)	Tartaric acid (0.2%).	Ignited tartaric acid.	Saccharic acid (0.2%).	Ignited saccharic acid.	Malic acid (1.0%).	Ignited malic acid.
0.6	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.6	1.4	0.65
1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.9	1.0
1.4	1.1	1.3	0.7	1.2	2.3	1.4
2.0	1.4	1.9	0.9	1.9	2.5	2.0

Confirmation of the Interfering Agent by the Paper Chromatography Method.—Thus, saccharic acid may be one of the agents chiefly responsible for the interference in Sanchis' test in water, treated by paddy husk carbon. As a confirmatory test for the organic acid, the paper chromatography method of Lugg and Overell (*Aus. J. Sci. Res.*, 1948, **1A**, 98) was used with modifications as applied to the mixed chromatography of Giri *et al.* (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1952, **34**, 95). A small circle of about 4 cm. diameter was drawn with a pencil from the centre of a circular filter paper. The elute from the anion exchanger (about 5μ l) was applied all along the circumference of the circle from the tip of a capillary tube. Four such spots were placed, leaving some space between the adjoining spots where known organic acids, viz., tartaric, saccharic, malic and oxalic acids were applied. After drying, the chromatogram was developed by running a mixture of butanol-acetic acid-water mixture from the centre. Next, bromophenol blue solution (0.04% in alcohol) was sprayed on the paper, when the location of the organic acids was shown as a small concentric yellow arc against a blue background. The arc of the elute joined with that of saccharic acid alone, thus confirming the test that saccharic acid is the interfering agent.

It is therefore advisable to test for saccharic acid as an interfering agent in Sanchis' test for fluorine when vegetable carbons are used for removal of fluorine from water.

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